

CoARA

Brief questionnaire

Before you start

We wish to welcome you to the Focus Group (FG) of TF3 of the WG ML and thank you in advance for your participation. The purpose of this brief questionnaire is to help us understand where your organisation stands in regard to implementing reforms in support of multilingual practices and addressing language biases in research assessment.

We would like you to provide us with information about the key steps your organisation has undertaken or has planned to undertake in order to raise awareness, implement and review actions in favour of language diversity in research.

If you need any further information about the work of our WG, please refer to the Annex or alternatively, email fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org.

Please proceed to the questionnaire.

Questionnaire

1. Since when did your organisation start working on supporting multilingualism policies and practices and combating language bias in research assessment?

- Prior to Signing CoARA - After Signing CoARA

Please explain in more detail when your activities started e.g. Month, Year.. (250 characters at the most)

2. Does your organisation have a **language policy** that considers research(er) assessment?

- Yes No

Please enter any information you consider being the starting point of the language policy and add links where possible (250 characters at the most)

3. Is the language policy concretely integrated in the internal assessment processes of your organisation?

- Yes No

If yes, please describe actions and practices in relation to concretely integrating the policy and provide links where possible (if publicly available) (500 characters at the most)

4. When assessing contributions to knowledge, does your organisation recognise and value outputs irrespective of language in which they are communicated?

- Yes No

If yes, provide examples of procedures and mechanisms put in place to recognise valuable contributions that researchers make to science and for the benefit of society irrespective of the language in which they are communicated. (500 characters at the most)

5. Do the members of your organisation (researchers, other employees...) face challenges and difficulties in adopting multilingualism practices?

- Yes No

If yes, please enter information about the profile of the individual(s) and the nature of the challenges they encounter.

6. In your organisation, are researchers in different disciplines and career stages involved in the development and review of the procedures, mechanisms and criteria that enable the recognition of research diversity, including from a language perspective?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

7. Does your organisation support the use of publication databases (e.g. OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, local CRIS or Repository) which take into consideration local languages?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

8. Does your organisation make sure that when metrics-based systems are used for different types of evaluation, publications in all languages are adequately taken into account?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

9. Does your organisation (as per the recommendations by DORA), during expert-based evaluation, value high quality research regardless of the publishing language or publication channel?

- Yes No I don't know

In this scenario, please provide an example where this has been the case - Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (500 characters at the most)

10. Does your organisation endorse the principle that writing in English does not confer a merit per se superior to publications in other languages?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

11. Does your organisation endorse that multilingualism favours the development of socially relevant research and contributes to sustaining cultural diversity?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

12. Does your organisation consider excellence in local research as relevant and value the use of local and national languages as high-quality literature to reward excellence, helping make such research available to all?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

13. When choosing evaluators, does your organisation ensure that they have required language skills to assess research outputs in relevant languages?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

14. Did your organisation endorse, beyond CoARA, also Helsinki, DORA or any other international declarations or initiatives?

- Yes No

Please add information in relation to which declaration or initiatives your organisation has signed. (250 characters at the most)

15. Does your organisation take language and potential language biases into consideration already when planning evaluation, assessment or funding procedures?

- Yes No

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)

16. Please provide any other feedback you consider is relevant.

Please enter any explanation you consider pertinent to this question (250 characters at the most)